

FIGURE 1-1
Site Location Map
Gowanus Canal Remedial Investigation
Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 1-2
Original Gowanus Creek and Wetland Complex
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Brooklyn, New York

FIGURE 1-3
Gowanus Canal and Adjacent Water Bodies
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Brooklyn, New York

LEGEND

- Fill
- Soft sediment
- Gowanus Creek native sediments

Not to scale.

FIGURE 1-4
 Conceptual Diagram of Sediment Deposits in the Gowanus Canal
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FIGURE 1-5
General Land Use – Current and Historic
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FIGURE 1-6
Stormwater/CSO Outfall Locations
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